

ON A PROBLEM OF F. SMARANDACHE*

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ABSTRACT. Let $d_s(n)$ denotes the sum of the base 10 digits of $n \in N$. For natural $x \geq 2$ and arbitrary fixed exponent $m \in N$, let $A_m(x) = \sum_{n < x} d_s^m(n)$. The main purpose of this paper is to give two exact calculating formulas for $A_1(x)$ and $A_2(x)$.

1. INTRODUCTION

For any positive integer n , let $d_s(n)$ denotes the sum of the base 10 digits of n . For example, $d_s(0) = 0, d_s(1) = 1, d_s(2) = 2, \dots, d_s(11) = 2, d_s(12) = 3, \dots$. In problem 21 of book [1], Professor F.Smaradache ask us to study the properties of sequence $\{d_s(n)\}$. For natural number $x \geq 2$ and arbitrary fixed exponent $m \in N$, let

$$A_m(x) = \sum_{n < x} d_s^m(n). \quad (1)$$

The main purpose of this paper is to study the calculating problem of $A_m(x)$, and use elementary methods to deduce two exact calculating formulas for $A_1(x)$ and $A_2(x)$. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. For any positive integer x , let $x = a_1 10^{k_1} + a_2 10^{k_2} + \dots + a_s 10^{k_s}$ with $k_1 > k_2 > \dots > k_s \geq 0$ and $1 \leq a_i \leq 9, i = 2, 3, \dots, s$. Then we have the calculating formulas

$$A_1(x) = \sum_{i=1}^s a_i \cdot \left(\frac{9}{2} k_i + \sum_{j=1}^i a_j - \frac{a_i + 1}{2} \right) \cdot 10^{k_i};$$

$$A_2(x) = \sum_{i=1}^s a_i \cdot \left[\frac{k_i(81k_i + 33)}{4} + \frac{9k_i}{2}(a_i - 1) + \sum_{j=1}^i a_j^2 - \frac{(4a_i - 1)(a_i + 1)}{6} \right] \cdot 10^{k_i}$$

$$+ \sum_{i=2}^s a_i \cdot \left[(9k_i - a_i - 1)10^{k_i} + 2 \sum_{j=i}^s a_j 10^{k_j} \right] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} a_j \right).$$

For general integer $m \geq 3$, using our methods we can also give an exact calculating formula for $A_m(x)$. But in these cases, the computations are more complex.

Key words and phrases. F.Smarandache problem; Sum of base 10 digits; Calculating formula.
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2. PROOF OF THE THEOREM

In this section, we complete the proof of the Theorem. First we need following two simple Lemmas.

Lemma 1. *For any integer $k \geq 0$, we have the identities*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{a)} \quad & A_1(10^k) = \frac{9}{2} \cdot k \cdot 10^k; \\ \text{b)} \quad & A_1(a \cdot 10^k) = \left(\frac{9}{2}k + \frac{a-1}{2} \right) \cdot a \cdot 10^k, \quad 1 \leq a \leq 9. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. We first prove a) of Lemma 1 by induction. For $k = 0$ and 1, we have $A_1(10^0) = A_1(1) = 0$, $A_1(10^1) = A_1(10) = 45$. So that the identity

$$A_1(10^k) = \sum_{n < 10^k} d_s(n) = \frac{9}{2} \cdot k \cdot 10^k \quad (2)$$

holds for $k = 0$ and 1. Assume (2) is true for $k = m - 1$. Then by the inductive assumption we have

$$\begin{aligned} A_1(10^m) &= \sum_{n < 9 \cdot 10^{m-1}} d_s(n) + \sum_{9 \cdot 10^{m-1} \leq n < 10^m} d_s(n) \\ &= A_1(9 \cdot 10^{m-1}) + \sum_{0 \leq n < 10^{m-1}} d_s(n + 9 \cdot 10^{m-1}) \\ &= A_1(9 \cdot 10^{m-1}) + \sum_{0 \leq n < 10^{m-1}} (d_s(n) + 9) \\ &= A_1(9 \cdot 10^{m-1}) + 9 \cdot 10^{m-1} + \sum_{n < 10^{m-1}} d_s(n) \\ &= A_1(9 \cdot 10^{m-1}) + 9 \cdot 10^{m-1} + A_1(10^{m-1}) \\ &= A_1(8 \cdot 10^{m-1}) + (8 + 9) \cdot 10^{m-1} + 2A_1(10^{m-1}) \\ &= \dots \dots \dots \\ &= (1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \cdot 10^{m-1} + 10A_1(10^{m-1}) \\ &= \frac{9}{2} \cdot 10^m + 10 \cdot \frac{9}{2} \cdot (m-1) \cdot 10^{m-1} \\ &= \frac{9}{2} \cdot m \cdot 10^m. \end{aligned}$$

That is, (2) is true for $k = m$. This proves the first part of Lemma 1.

The second part b) follows from a) of Lemma 1 and the recurrence formula

$$\begin{aligned} A_1(a \cdot 10^k) &= \sum_{n < (a-1) \cdot 10^k} d_s(n) + \sum_{(a-1) \cdot 10^k \leq n < a \cdot 10^k} d_s(n) \\ &= \sum_{n < (a-1) \cdot 10^k} d_s(n) + \sum_{0 \leq n < 10^k} d_s(n + (a-1) \cdot 10^k) \\ &= \sum_{n < (a-1) \cdot 10^k} a(n) + (a-1) \cdot 10^k + \sum_{n < 10^k} d_s(n) \\ &= A_1((a-1) \cdot 10^k) + (a-1) \cdot 10^k + A_1(10^k). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Lemma 1.

Lemma 2. For any integer $k \geq 0$ and $1 \leq a \leq 9$, we have the identities

$$c) \quad A_2(10^k) = \frac{81k + 33}{4} \cdot k \cdot 10^k;$$

$$d) \quad A_2(a \cdot 10^k) = \left[\frac{k(81k + 33)}{4} + \frac{9k}{2}(a - 1) + \frac{(a - 1)(2a - 1)}{6} \right] \cdot a \cdot 10^k.$$

Proof. These results can be deduced by Lemma 1, induction and the recurrence formula

$$\begin{aligned} A_2(10^{k+1}) &= \sum_{n < 9 \cdot 10^k} d_s^2(n) + \sum_{9 \cdot 10^k \leq n < 10^{k+1}} d_s^2(n) \\ &= \sum_{n < 9 \cdot 10^k} d_s^2(n) + \sum_{0 \leq n < 10^k} d_s^2(n + 9 \cdot 10^k) \\ &= \sum_{n < 9 \cdot 10^k} d_s^2(n) + \sum_{0 \leq n < 10^k} (d_s(n) + 9)^2 \\ &= A_2(9 \cdot 10^k) + 9^2 \cdot 10^k + 18A_1(10^k) + A_2(10^k) \\ &= \dots\dots\dots \\ &= 10A_2(10^k) + (1^2 + 2^2 + \dots + 9^2) \cdot 10^k + 2 \cdot (1 + 2 + \dots + 9)A_1(10^k) \\ &= 10A_2(10^k) + \frac{57}{2} \cdot 10^{k+1} + 90 \cdot \frac{9}{2} \cdot k \cdot 10^k \\ &= 10A_2(10^k) + \frac{57}{2} \cdot 10^{k+1} + \frac{81}{2} \cdot k \cdot 10^{k+1}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Lemma 2.

Now we use Lemma 1 and Lemma 2 to complete the proof of the Theorem. For any positive integer x , let $x = a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1} + a_2 \cdot 10^{k_2} + \dots + a_s \cdot 10^{k_s}$, with $k_1 > k_2 > \dots > k_s \geq 0$ under the base 10. Then applying Lemma 1 repeatedly we have

$$\begin{aligned} A_1(x) &= \sum_{n < a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}} d_s(n) + \sum_{a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1} \leq n < x} d_s(n) \\ &= A_1(a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) + \sum_{0 \leq n < x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}} d_s(n + a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) \\ &= A_1(a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) + \sum_{0 \leq n < x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}} (d_s(n) + a_1) \\ &= A_1(a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) + a_1(x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) + \sum_{0 \leq n < x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}} d_s(n) \\ &= A_1(a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) + a_1(x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) + A_1(x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) \\ &= A_1(a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) + A_1(a_2 \cdot 10^{k_2}) + a_1(x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) \\ &\quad + a_2(x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1} - a_2 \cdot 10^{k_2}) + A_1(x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1} - a_2 \cdot 10^{k_2}) \\ &= \dots\dots\dots \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{i=1}^s A_1(a_i \cdot 10^{k_i}) + \sum_{i=1}^s a_i \left(x - \sum_{j=1}^i a_j \cdot 10^{k_j} \right) \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^s \left(\frac{9}{2} \cdot k_i + \frac{a_i - 1}{2} \right) \cdot a_i \cdot 10^{k_i} + \sum_{i=2}^s a_i \cdot 10^{k_i} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} a_j \right) \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^s \left(\frac{9}{2} k_i + \sum_{j=1}^i a_j - \frac{a_i + 1}{2} \right) \cdot a_i \cdot 10^{k_i}.
\end{aligned}$$

This proves the first part of the Theorem.

Applying Lemma 2 and the first part of the Theorem repeatedly we have

$$\begin{aligned}
A_2(x) &= \sum_{n < a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}} d_s^2(n) + \sum_{a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1} \leq n < x} d_s^2(n) \\
&= A_2(a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) + \sum_{0 \leq n < x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}} d_s^2(n + a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) \\
&= A_2(a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) + \sum_{0 \leq n < x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}} (d_s(n) + a_1)^2 \\
&= A_2(a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) + \sum_{0 \leq n < x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}} (d_s^2(n) + 2a_1 \cdot d_s(n) + a_1^2) \\
&= A_2(a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) + a_1^2 \cdot (x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) \\
&\quad + 2a_1 A_1(x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) + A_2(x - a_1 \cdot 10^{k_1}) \\
&= \dots \dots \dots \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^s A_2(a_i \cdot 10^{k_i}) + \sum_{i=1}^s a_i^2 \left(x - \sum_{j=1}^i a_j \cdot 10^{k_j} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^s 2a_i A_1 \left(x - \sum_{j=1}^i a_j \cdot 10^{k_j} \right) \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^s \left[\frac{k_i(81k_i + 33)}{4} + \frac{9k_i}{2}(a_i - 1) + \frac{(a_i - 1)(2a_i - 1)}{6} \right] \cdot a_i \cdot 10^{k_i} \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=2}^s a_i \cdot 10^{k_i} \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} a_j^2 \right) + \sum_{i=2}^s (9k_i + a_i - 1) \cdot a_i \cdot 10^{k_i} \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} a_j \right) \\
&\quad + 2 \sum_{i=2}^s \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} a_j \right) \cdot a_i \cdot \left(x - \sum_{j=1}^i a_j \cdot 10^{k_j} \right) \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^s \left[\frac{k_i(81k_i + 33)}{4} + \frac{9k_i}{2}(a_i - 1) + \sum_{j=1}^i a_j^2 - \frac{(4a_i - 1)(a_i + 1)}{6} \right] \cdot a_i \cdot 10^{k_i} \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=2}^s a_i \cdot \left[(9k_i - a_i - 1)10^{k_i} + 2 \sum_{j=i}^s a_j 10^{k_j} \right] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} a_j \right).
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the second part of the Theorem.

REFERENCES

1. F. Smarandache, *Only problems, not Solutions*, Xiquan Publ. House, Chicago, 1993, pp. 22.
2. Tom M. Apostol, *Introduction to Analytic Number Theory*, Springer-Verlag, New York, 1976.
3. "Smarandache Sequences" at <http://www.gallup.unm.edu/~smarandache/snaqint.txt>.
4. "Smarandache Sequences" at <http://www.gallup.unm.edu/~smarandache/snaqint2.txt>.
5. "Smarandache Sequences" at <http://www.gallup.unm.edu/~smarandache/snaqint3.txt>.